

Population Characteristics of Malegaon & Nandgaon Tahsils of Nashik District

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Abstract: In this research paper the researcher has studied the characteristics of population of Malegaon and Nandgaon tahsils of Nashik district. The geographical data analysis technique has been used for calculating the results of this paper. Total population of the district having analyzed compared with reference to the census 2001 & 2011. The tahsil wise decadal growth of the Nashik district in 2001 and 2011 compared and. The R growth rate formula has been used to calculate the population growth rate. The data has been tabulated maps have been incorporated at the place. Rural population growth rate as well as urban population growth rate in the Nashik district has been calculated in the decade 2001 and 2011

Introduction

India is a second largest populated country of the world; there were 1210726932 as per 2011 census. Maharashtra state is a second largest populated state of the country, Maharashtra state total population was 112374333 as per 2011 census. The Nashik district is fourth largest populated district of the state; there were 6107187 total populations as per the 2011 census. And Malegaon tahsil is second largest tahsil of the district i.e. 955594. And Nandgaon tahsil is fifth largest populated tahsil of the district. The total population of the tahsil was 288848 as per 2011 census.

Study Area

Study area are situated in the east part of the district, lies between 20° 00' N To 20° 53' North latitudinal and from 74° 21' E to 74° 56' East longitudinal extension, with the total geographical area of 2919.62 sq. km. According to census 2011, 1244442 total population of the study area, to the east of study area is Jalgaon & Dhule district, on the western side are Satana, Deola and Chandwad tahsils (Nashik District) Aurangabad is at the south east, Yeola tahsil is south. Malegaon and Nandgaon both tahsils are situated in the east part of the district

. Map. No.1 Location Map

Methodology-

Methodology is one of the significant part of analysis result of analysis highly depend on the

methodology will be used for the data analysis purpose. The present study is based on the secondary source of data.

Objectives

- 1) To study the population characteristics in the study area
- 2) To study the tahsil wise population of the district
- 3) To study the rural urban population of the study area.

Table No. 1: Tahsil wise total population of the district as per census 2001 & 2011

Sr. No.	Tahsils	Total population	
		2001	2011
1	Surgana	145135	175816
2	Kalwan	168403	208362
3	Deola	127194	144522
4	Baglan	311395	374435
5	Malegaon	789230	955594
6	Nandgaon	236319	288848
7	Chandvad	205189	235849
8	Dindori	264727	315709
9	Peth	96774	119838
10	Trimbakeshwar	136417	168423
11	Nashik	1317367	1755491
12	Igatpuri	228208	253513
13	Sinnar	292075	346390
14	Niphad	439842	493251
15	Yeola	235521	271146
	Nashik Total:	4993796	6107187

(Source – Census 2001, 2011)

As per censuses of 2001 the total population of Nashik district was 4993796. Then a decadal later in 2011 it was increased with 1113391 and was 6107187. The rate of growth in this decade was a 22.29%. Out of 2001 the population of Malegaon tahsil was 789230. And

then a decade later in 2011 it was increased with 166364 and was 789230. The rate of growth in this decade was a 21.07%. And the total population of the Nandgaon tahsil was 236319. Then the 2011 it was increase 52529. And was 288848. It means decadal growth of 22.23 %.

Figure No. 1 as per census 2001 & 2011 Tahsil wise Population of the Nashik district.

Figure No. 2 Tahsil wise Decadal Growth in Nashik district

Above the figure No. 1 we can see that the different between 2001 to 2011 total population of district with tahsil wise. After the Nashik tahsil, Malegaon tahsil is highly populated tahsil of the district and Nandgaon tahsil is fifth largest populated tahsil of the district.

Tahsil wise decadal growth of the Nashik district

As per census of 2001 the total population of Nashik district was 4993796 and 6107187 as per

the 2011 census. Which means the increase in population in this decade was 22.29 %. And the total population of the Malegaon tahsil was 789230. And then a decade later in 2011 it was increased with 166364 and was 789230.the rate of growth in this decade was a 21.07%. And the total population of the Nandgaon tahsil was 236319. Then the 2011 it was increase 52529. And was 288848. It means decadal growth of 22.23 %.

Table No. 2: Tahsil wise population decadal growth in Nashik district

Sr. No.	Tahsils	Total population		Decadal growth 2001 to 2011
		2001	2011	
1	Surgana	145135	175816	21.13
2	Kalwan	168403	208362	23.72
3	Deola	127194	144522	13.62
4	Baglan	311395	374435	20.24
5	Malegaon	789230	955594	21.07
6	Nandgaon	236319	288848	22.23
7	Chandvad	205189	235849	14.94
8	Dindori	264727	315709	19.25
9	Peint	96774	119838	23.83
10	Trimbakeshwar	136417	168423	23.46
11	Nashik	1317367	1755491	33.25
12	Igatpuri	228208	253513	11.08
13	Sinnar	292075	346390	18.59
14	Niphad	439842	493251	12.14
15	Yeola	235521	271146	15.12
Nashik Total:		4993796	6107187	22.29

(Source – Census 2001, 2011 computed by researcher)

The following formula applied to calculate the growth rate of population

$$R = \frac{P_n - P_0}{P_0} \times 100$$

Where;

R = growth rate of population.

P_n = current years population

P₁ = Base year population

Table presents the tahsil wise population growth in Nashik district from 2001 to 2011. According to decadal growth of more than 20 are Surgana, Kalwan, Baglan, Malegaon, Nandgaon, Peint, Trimbakeshwar, and Nashik tahsil and whole district also. Deola, Chandwad, Dindori,

Igatpuri, sinner, Niphad, and Yeola tahsils population growth is lower than average of Nashik districting. That is less than 20. Specially Malegaon and Nandgaon both tahsil as well as total district average population growth rate is between 21 to 23% , Malegaon tahsil are

populated as compare to Nandgaon tahsil, Malegaon tahsil population 166364 it has increased so much in between 2001 to 2011.

As shown Figure No. 2 in the above table, there is a decade increase from 2001 to 2011, according to the tahsils wise of the district. As shown above, the highest increase in Nashik tahsil is seen, 33.25% increase. After this, there is an increase of 23% in the Kalwan, Peint and Trimbakeshwar tahsils, followed by Surgana, Baglan, Malegaon, Nandgaon those tehsils with 20 to 22% increase. And tahsil of Deola, Chandwad, Dindori Igatpuri, Sinnar, Niphad and Yeola has increased by 10 to 20%. The average increase in the district is 22.29%. From the above mentioned detailed the study area we can say the increase in population was Nashik district increase in population from 2011 to 2011 was 22.29 % , and Malegaon tahsil increasing population from 21.07 % and Nandgaon tahsil increase of 22.23 % ,

Map No. 1 Population Growth rate Map 2001-2011

Table No. 3: Tahsil wise Rural and Urban population in Nashik district 2001 to 2011

Sr. No.	Tahsils	Population					
		2001			2011		
		Total	Rural	Urban	Total	Rural	Urban
1	Surgana	145135	138988	6147	175816	169553	6263
2	Kalwan	168403	168403	0	208362	208362	0
3	Deola	127194	127194	0	144522	144522	0
4	Baglan	311395	278834	32561	374435	336734	37701
5	Malegaon	789230	333176	456054	955594	368137	587457
6	Nandgaon	236319	140723	95596	288848	185186	103662
7	Chandvad	205189	205189	0	235849	210508	25341
8	Dindori	264727	264727	0	315709	315709	0
9	Peint	96774	96774	0	119838	119838	0
10	Trimbakeshwar	136417	126613	9804	168423	156367	12056
11	Nashik	1317367	165041	1152326	1755491	175948	1579543
12	Igatpuri	228208	176463	51745	253513	197686	55827
13	Sinnar	292075	260445	31630	346390	281091	65299
14	Niphad	439842	381356	58486	493251	418853	74398
15	Yeola	235521	192314	43207	271146	221320	49826
	Total dist.	4993796	3056240	1937556	6107187	3509814	2597373

(Source – Population Survey Report in 2001 and 2011)

As per census 2001 and 2011 above the table showing total population of the district with tahsil wise, and describe the rural and urban population of the tahsil wise of the district. Population of district is very highly growth of all tahsils of the district. According to 2011 total population of the district was 6107187. And census 2001 the total population of the district

was 4993796, it means in between those ten years (decadal) 1113391 increase the population of the tahsil. About Malegaon tahsil there was 166364 people's population increases, it means 21.07 % population was growth. And Nandgaon tahsil 52529 numbers of peoples was increase it means 22.23 % growth of the tahsil.

Table No. 4: Tahsil wise rural population growth in Nashik district 2001 to 2011

Sr.No.	Tahsils	Population (Rural)		Growth Rate (%) 2001 to 2011
		2001	2011	
1	Surgana	138988	169553	21.99

2	Kalwan	168403	208362	23.72
3	Deola	127194	144522	13.62
4	Baglan	278834	336734	20.76
5	Malegaon	333176	368137	10.49
6	Nandgaon	140723	185186	31.59
7	Chandvad	205189	210508	2.59
8	Dindori	264727	315709	19.25
9	Peint	96774	119838	23.83
10	Trimbakeshwar	126613	156367	23.49
11	Nashik	165041	175948	6.60
12	Igatpuri	176463	197686	12.02
13	Sinner	260445	281091	7.93
14	Niphad	381356	418853	9.83
15	Yeola	192314	221320	15.08
	Total	3056240	3509814	14.84

(Source – Census 2001, 2011 computed by researcher)

As shown in the above table, rural population growth has been shown in the tahsil wise of Nashik district, 14.84 has been average population growth of Nashik district. In which the highest population growth of Nandgaon tahsil has increased in the whole district, it is 31.59 percent. And lowest in the district is 2.59 percent of Chandwad tahsil has increased, There has been an increase in tahsils of Chandwad,

Nashik, Sinner and Niphad by 5 to 10 percent, after this, between 10 to 15 percent there has been an increase in Deola, Malegaon and Igatpuri tahsils, then, there has an increase of Yeola, Dindori tahsils between 15 to 20 percent, after this, there has been an increase in between 20 to 25 percent in Surgana, Kalwan, Baglan, Peth and Trimbakeshwar tahsils, and more than 25 percent has increase only in Nandgaon tahsil.

Table No. 5: Tahsil wise urban population growth in Nashik district 2001 to 2011

Sr.No.	Tahsils	Population (Urban)		Growth Rate (%) 2001 to 2011
		2001	2011	
1	Surgana	6,147	6,263	1.88
2	Kalwan	0	0	0
3	Deola	0	0	0
4	Baglan	32,561	37,701	15.78
5	Malegaon	456,054	587,457	28.81
6	Nandgaon	95,596	103,662	8.43
7	Chandvad	0	25,341	-
8	Dindori	0	0	0
9	Peint	0	0	0
10	Trimbakeshwar	9,804	12,056	22.97
11	Nashik	1,152,326	1,579,543	37.07
12	Igatpuri	51,745	55,827	7.89
13	Sinner	31,630	65,299	106.44
14	Niphad	58,486	74,398	27.20
15	Yeola	43,207	49,826	15.31
	Total	1,937,556	2,597,373	34.05

(Source – Census 2001, 2011 computed by researcher)

As shown in the table above, tahsil wise urban population growth rate of Nashik district, in between 2001 to 2011 census, in the whole Nashik district 34.05 percent average urban population increased. In the district sinner tahsil is highest urban population growth rate, and lowest in Surgana tahsil observed, i.e. only 1.88

percent. According to census 2001, Chandwad tahsil there was no urban population, but according to 2011 census this tahsil has been given the status of urban city, that's why it is seen as increase the number of population, the urban population is zero in Kalwan, Deola, Dindory and Peth of those four tahsils, there has

been an increase of Surgana tahsil by 1 to 5 percent, after that, there has been an increase of Nandgaon and Igatpuri tahsils 5 to 10 percent, Yeola and Baglan tahsil 15 to 20 percent, Trimbakeshwar 20 to 25 percent, Niphad, Sinner, Nashik, and Malegaon tahsils has been an increase in more than 25 percent.

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